
**Library Users' Information Search Habits:
An Analytical Study of CMR Group of
Institutions in Hyderabad**

Ravi Kumar Giyyar

Librarian

CMR Technical Campus, Kandlakoya, Medchal
Road, Hyderabad, Telangana-501401

Email: librarian@cmrtc.ac.in

Raja Suresh Kumar Pitla

Librarian

CMR Institute of Technology,
Kandlakoya, Medchal Road, Hyderabad,
Telangana-501401

Email: rajasureshkumar.pitla@cmritonline.ac.in

Abstract

The primary purpose of a university library is to meet the needs of its many students and faculty as quickly as possible without sacrificing service quality. A technical university's library is crucial to the institution's continuous research. The Engineering College Library's purpose is to serve the needs of its many patrons, including professors, students, and the general public. This paper aims to quantify the information-seeking habits of engineering college library users at the CMR Group of institutions and libraries to its students and faculty. Over 85% of users access e-resources to learn or conduct research. Exam preparation aids are used by 48.60% of students. The survey results will aid library staff in improving the materials and services they offer its patrons.

Keywords

Information-seeking Behaviour; Library Utilization;
Engineering faculty and Students; e-resources

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1. INTRODUCTION

Information refers to several arrays of ideas and facts transferred through Communication to acquire knowledge, which plays an essential role in human history in all civilisations. The library is a key source for acquiring knowledge. But due to the development of information communication technology (ICT), academic libraries face several challenges. The users are well aware of a variety of available information resources. So, expectations are increasing to get more information along with documents from the library. It is essential to regularly re-shelve the library information as per user requirements. Mahapatra (2014) explained that, "library being a service institution should be offer information to its users. User's perception is to get complete information in the library. As the Merriam-Webster dictionary mentions, perception is "a feeling or belief about how good something will be". To rationalise the user's requirements-seeking behaviour plays an important role. Information-seeking behaviour is the purpose of seeking information from a library to satisfy some goal by collecting information through books, periodicals, and computer-based systems like e-journals, e-news, e-books and e-database . Behaviour information collected from various surveys has to be analysed to understand how they should be addressed to provide relevant information to users.

2. Literature Review

Information searching habits as a social behavior happen when the user apprehends the need to obtain relative information and consciously acquires action to determine what required Agarwal (2018), Biradar and Sampath Kumar (2018) show the nearly half of faculty and students are fulfilled with library lending service and have good view about book bank facility of their college library. Aravind and Kavitha's (2020) study provides an improved acceptance of concepts of bibliotherapy and commend the librarian by providing an explanation of and a rationale for utilising bibliotherapy offered by public libraries. Resent technological growth has added digital resources to the libraries' holdings. These are referred as 'E-Resources' (Kumar and Tholkappian, (2013). Raja Suresh Kumar and others (2020) found that the majority of engineering college faculty use IEEE, SCOPUS, Springer, and NPTEL Services as e-resources for their academic and Research Purposes. Raja Suresh Kumar and others. (2018) found that most library users know and use N-List resources for their Academic Purposes. Ravi Kumar and others

(2021) that 44.26% of KIET Group of Institute Library Users visit the library for circulation purposes through lending services, as they mentioned that the major difficulty in gathering information is information too vast in online resources. Suresh Babu, M. and Raja Suresh Kumar, Pitla. (2021) revealed that most of the GRIET Faculty Using IEEE and J Gate Resources for their needed information for academics

3. CMR Group of Institutions

CMR Group of Institutions is one of the leading educational institutions in the Telangana State under the sponsor of MGR Educational CMRGI (2023) Society, dedicated to imparting quality education and promoting excellence in academic pursuits in the field of Science, Pharmacy, Engineering Management, in a sprawling 70-acre campus at Kandlakoya village, Medchal Mandal and Dist. All four colleges were accredited by NAAC (National Assessment and Accreditation Council), NBA(National Board of Accreditation) and An autonomous body and granted by UGC.The Colleges offers courses like Bachelor of Technology (B.Tech), Master of Technology(M.Tech), Master of Business Administration(MBA) and Pharmacy. The college's Central Libraries have an affluent collection of Books, Journals, and Databases with Electronic. The Libraries also has back volumes of periodicals. Access to around 3500 full-text e- Journals. The Libraries are members of DELNET, NDL and N- List for accessing the bibliographical databases of e-books, e-journals, e- theses, etc. The libraries have institutional repositories portals for NPTEL lectures, MIT course lectures, e-books, etc. CMR Group of Institutions has a very good and well-organised collection and services that cater to the informational requirements of the faculty, students, and other staff of the Institutions. The existing state of the library is mentioned below

Table 1: Status of CMR Group of College libraries

Resources/ College	CRM CET	CMRIT	CMRTC	CMREC
Books	76382	51782	35603	32228
Print Journals	144	147	148	116
E- Journals	11752	15112	6724	7112
E- Books	17173	15173	16129	16129
CD ROMS	4563	4810	3948	3743
Back Volumes	2583	1970	1534	1549

4. Research Objectives:

The study observes the information search habits of the users in 4 Engineering Colleges in the CMR Group of Institutions; in particular, the main focus is on acquiring information about the nature of educational information necessary, the sources sought advice from and the common outline of the information searching system by the users. Further specially, the main Objectives of the study are

- To discover the purpose of visiting the CMR group of engineering institution libraries
- To recognise what type of Information Sources and Services are provided by CMR Group of college libraries
- To identify the predicament users face while utilising facilities, services and sources of CMR Group of Institution Libraries.

5. Research Methods and Limitations

The extent of the Present paper is limited to the engineering faculty and students of four engineering colleges in the CMR Group of Institutions. The faculty and students of the study are comprised of various engineering and technology departments. The secondary sources are an assortment of articles, reports, books and journals. The necessary primary data about Libraries are accumulated from library users by questionnaire method. Through a set of question questionnaires issued the library users of different branches of engineering. Analysed the data with SPSS 2023.

Response Received: Information is essential for research, and education is supported by exhaustive and timely information. The views of 800 users, 400 faculty, and 400 students were considered to present their opinions on the various aspects of the information-seeking behaviour of libraries and information service facilities of libraries. The response rate was 93.625% as shown in Table 2

Table: 2 Sample Size

S No	College Name	Questionnaires Distributed			Questionnaire Received			Percentage
		Faculty	Students	Total	Faculty	Students	Total	
1	CMR College of Engineering & Technology (CMRCET)	50	150	200	34	148	182	91.00
2	CMR Institute of Technology (CMRIT)	50	150	200	44	147	191	95.50
3	CMR Technical Campus (CMRTC)	50	150	200	42	147	189	94.50
4	CMR Engineering College (CMREC)	50	150	200	42	145	187	93.50
Total		200	600	800	162	587	749	93.63
Response Rate 93.63%								

There are 200 faculty members and 600 students, 800 of which were distributed online questionnaires, and 749 responses were received. The total response is 93.63%. The data analysis software utilised is SPSS 23. Statistical tests found of the chi-square test are achieved to evaluate actual results with predictions. This test's goal is to create whether a disagreement between observed and expected data results from chance or a connection among the variables under the study formula

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{(E_i)}$$

χ^2 = Chi-Squared

O_i = Observed Value

E_i = Expected Value

6. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

6.1 Profile of Sample:

When we give the impression of the creature at the voice in the situation, it could, in this case, be a question of gender and social status the gender influences their reading habit. The Demographic details of the Sample are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Demographic Distribution of Respondents

Demographic Details		Status		TOTAL
		Student	Faculty	
Gender	Male	390 (52.07)	104 (13.89)	494 (65.95)
	Female	197 (26.30)	58 (7.74)	255 (34.05)
Age	Below 20 Years	502 (67.02)	0	502 (67.02)
	21 to 25	81	3	84

Years	Years	(10.81)	(0.40)	(11.21)
	26 to 30 Years	4 (0.53)	36 (4.81)	40 (5.34)
	31 to 35 Years	0	72 (9.61)	72 (9.61)
	Above 36 Years	0	51 (6.81)	51 (6.81)
Qualification	UG	573 (76.50)	0	573 (76.50)
	PG	14 (1.87)	130 (17.36)	144 (19.23)
	PHD	0	32 (4.27)	32 (4.27)
Total		587 (78.37)	162 (21.63)	749 (100.00)

(Figures in parenthesis indicate percentages).

As mentioned in Table 2, 65.95% of users are male, and only 34.05% are female; 67.02% of those surveyed were under the age of 20, 11.21% were between the ages of 21 to 25 Years, 5.34% were between the ages of 26 and 30, 9.61% were between the ages of 31 and 35, and 6.81% were aged 36 and up. Most of the users were under the age of 20. It also shows user qualifications. 76.50% of users were U.G., 19.23% were PG, and 4.27% were Ph.D. Among students, 76.50% had U.G. degrees, and 1.87% had P.G. degrees. Only 4.27% of faculty members have PhDs. Most participants are students. Observing, it's clear that the majority of library users were undergraduates.

6.2 Sources of Information

Information is a primary source for any professional movement. Particular information is an objective-centric demand of the users. The needs of information may vary along with users depending upon their work nature. The research of users approach to trace

needed information helps to progress the information service. Table 4 shows which type of information

sources are trying when seeking information.

Table: 4 Sources of Information

Source	Students	Staff	TOTAL	Chi-Square	D.F	Significance
Discussion with colleagues	142 (18.96)	99 (13.22)	241 (32.18)	140.780	14	0.000 Significant
Consult a knowledge person in the field	232 (30.97)	78 (10.41)	310 (41.39)			
Consult Supervisor	142 (18.96)	24 (3.20)	166 (22.16)			
Primary Journals	454 (60.61)	149 (19.89)	603 (80.51)			
Indexing Journals	489 (65.29)	98 (13.08)	587 (78.37)			
Review Journals	284 (37.92)	124 (16.56)	408 (54.47)			
Web resources	547 (73.03)	148 (19.76)	695 (92.79)			
Technical Reports	187 (24.97)	74 (9.88)	261 (34.85)			
Library OPAC	397 (53.00)	137 (18.29)	534 (71.30)			
Text Books	482 (64.35)	141 (18.83)	623 (83.18)			
E- Resources	479 (63.95)	158 (21.09)	637 (85.05)			
Abstracting Journals	478 (63.82)	128 (17.09)	606 (80.91)			
Reference Sources	274 (36.58)	134 (17.89)	408 (54.47)			
Conference Proceedings	296 (39.52)	139 (18.56)	435 (58.08)			
Thesis/ Dissertations	178 (23.77)	119 (15.89)	297 (39.65)			
TOTAL	587 (78.37)	162 (21.63)	749 (100.00)			

(Multiple choices has given to users) (Figures in parenthesis indicate percentages).

Figure: 1 Sources of Information

from the above table 4 and Figure 1 it is evident that the majority of users 92.79% of users use web

Resources, 85.05% Uses e-resources for getting Information for academics and research, and 83.18% of users use textbooks, Kadli and Hanchinal (2015) pointed out on the information seeking behaviour of their students through textbooks, 80.91% use through abstracting journals, 80.51% of users use primary journals, 78.37% through indexing journals, 71.30% through OPAC, 58.08% through Conference Proceedings, 54.47% through Reference Sources and review journals, 41.39% consult a knowledge person in the field, 39.65% through Thesis/ dissertations, 34.85% of users through technical reports, 32.18% of users discuss with colleagues, and 22.16% of users consult with supervisor.

For additional discussion, the calculated chi-square value is 140.780, is Greater than the Chi-Square table value of 23.685 with 14 Degrees of Freedom when the significance level is $p < 0.05$. As a result, the difference in respondents' working status was identified as statistically significant in sources of information with type of users.

6.3 Purpose of seeking information

The library offers diverse types of services to meet the users' requirements, including reference services; their interest influences the purpose of reading. The library services provided to the users should perform their functionality satisfactorily. Table 5 shows the purpose of seeking information.

Table: 5 Purpose of Seeking Information

Purpose	Students	Staff	TOTAL	Chi-Square	D.F	Significance
For preparing examination	364 (48.60)	0	364 (48.60)	266.626	7	0.000 Significant
For updating knowledge	54 (7.21)	47 (6.28)	101 (13.48)			
For writing assignment	67 (8.95)	23 (3.07)	90 (12.02)			
For writing paper	21 (2.80)	25 (3.34)	46 (6.14)			
For Preparing for competitive exams	37 (4.94)	4 (0.53)	41 (5.47)			
For Preparing Class Notes	14 (1.87)	32 (4.27)	46 (6.14)			
For Preparing Projects & PPTs	13 (1.74)	19 (2.54)	32 (4.27)			
For Seminar & Conference	17 (2.27)	12 (1.60)	29 (3.87)			
TOTAL	587 (78.37)	162 (21.63)	749 (100.00)			

(Figures in parenthesis indicate percentages).

Figure: 2 Purpose of seeking information

From table 5 and figure 2, 48.60% students Uses Resources for preparing examination, 13.48% of users use for updating knowledge, 12.02% uses for writing assignment, 6.41% for writing paper and

preparing class notes, 4.27% of users use resources for preparing projects & PPTs About 3.87% uses least priority for prepare seminars and conferences. Coming to staff majority of staff seeking for update their knowledge, for further discussion using the chi-square test, the calculated chi-square value is 266.626, which is greater than the Chi-Square, Table value of 14.067 when the significance level is set at $p < 0.05$. This value can be used for further discussion. As a result, the difference in respondents' purpose of seeking information is statistically significant.

6.4 Problems faced by the user in utilizing the library services

Table: 6 Problems faced by the Users in utilizing the library services

Services	Students	Staff	TOTAL	Chi-Square	D.F	Significance
Material non available	14 (1.87)	1 (0.13)	15 (2.00)	203.950	9	0.000 Significant
Library staff services not Satisfied	2 (0.27)	4 (0.53)	6 (0.80)			
Insufficient Information	4 (0.53)	24 (3.20)	28 (3.74)			
Lack of time	87 (11.62)	74 (9.88)	161 (21.50)			
Do not know how to use the catalogue	17 (2.27)	7 (0.93)	24 (3.20)			
Lack of knowledge in using the library resources	48 (6.41)	12 (1.60)	60 (8.01)			
Information scattered in too many sources	184 (24.57)	13 (1.74)	197 (26.30)			
Information is too vast	193 (25.77)	11 (1.47)	204 (27.24)			
Some of information materials are old and outdated	24 (3.20)	16 (2.14)	40 (5.34)			
Accessibility problems	14 (1.87)	0 (0.00)	14 (1.87)			
TOTAL	587 (78.37)	162 (21.63)	749 (100.00)			

(Figures in parenthesis indicate percentages).

Figure: 3 Problems faced by the Users in utilizing the library services

It is observed in table 6 and figure 3 that the majority of users 27.24% feel information is too vast, 26.30% Faces problem due to information sprinkled in too many sources, lack of time, 21.50% of users faces problem as lack of time, 8.01% faces as lack of knowledge while using the resources of library, 5.34% faces as some of available information resources are old and redundant, 3.74% faces as insufficient information, 3.20% faces as users dont

know how to search the catalogue, 2.00% of uses feel material non available, 1.87% of users faces accessibility problems, 0.80% of users faces with library staff services. Coming to faculty majority of staff feel lack of time to search the information. Such as the chi-square χ^2 value of 203.950 is upper than 0.050 at 9 Degrees of Freedom, which is more than 16.919, when the significance level is set at $p < 0.05$. This value can be used for further discussion. As a result, the difference in respondents' Problems facing while using information seeking' is statistically significant. Problems facing while using information seeking' drawbacks aren't influenced by the fact that people are in different jobs.

7. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study was to investigate research topics on the information-searching habits of library patrons and the reading ability of library clients. The researchers found that the lives of the students and teachers who took part in the study were improved as a result of making use of library resources as part of a library programme. According to the participants, the objectives of the research were accomplished through the use of library resources that were referred to by

human readers. In order for library professionals to understand the requirements of their customers, user studies need to be carried out on a regular basis. The users expressed a high level of enthusiasm about taking part in the poll. The results of the survey will allow the library staff to submit a proposal for managing authorises constructing new facilities in the libraries. These new facilities will be based on the findings of the survey. User studies allow for the communication of the requirements that users have of the library. This sample survey was conducted among those who use engineering institutions, and it informed those individuals about the resources that are already available to them. The library ought to go out and get new editions of the most recent materials. The vast majority of the pupils have asked for a video presentation on the most current events. These kinds of surveys will be helpful to library professionals in terms of offering better resources and services to the users. They will also be helpful in gaining a better feel of the environment in which the library functions, understanding values, originating a vision statement, setting the strategic goals, evaluating, and reporting. According to the findings of a study, research of this kind assists libraries in receiving useful feedback and, as a result, in improving the quality of library services. The employees of the library should convince academics to master the most recent information-seeking methods and techniques, and they should also encourage academics to make greater use of the library's services and resources.

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